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INFORM ME: DESIGNING AN AGENT-BASED WEB INFORMATION RETRIEVAL SERVICE IN THE CONTEXT OF URBAN MOBILE USERS

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ABSTRACT

Thanks for the further development of ubiquitous computing technology and the advent of smartphone, the user behaviors are becoming more dynamic, diverse in terms of their access, gather and use of information within the urban areas. However, current web based information retrieval services still use the same methodologies and processes that were developed in a decade ago and these perspectives requires heavy cognitive loads with continuous strategic decision in order to get appropriate search results. To address this problem, we designed a smart agent-based information retrieval service focusing on the context of mobile phone users in crowded, complex urban areas.

Keywords: information retrieval, intelligent agent, ontology, adaptiveness, user interface design

INTRODUCTION

We are living in the era of ubiquitous computing and we are urban nomads seeking for tremendous information with our smart phones in everyday. Naturally, smart phones became one of our essential everyday gadgets and these devices are changing our behaviors especially in retrieval, acquisition and usage of information. From the middle of crowded subway to in the hallway of large shopping malls peeking around to buy, there are tremendous agenda to search within the urban areas for various purposes such as economic, entertainment or medical reasons. However, current web based information retrieval services are stay behind in the presuming the

context of users as if they always are in front of desktop computers. Even worse, these search services are still adopting the same methodologies and process that were developed in a decade ago putting people to under high cognitive loads. Because they need continuous strategic decision makings in order to get appropriate search results. Our agent based information retrieval service Inform Me was intended to address three fundamental research questions on this perspective:

- 1) What are the major factors that influence the behaviors of mobile users especially in complex, urbanized areas?*
- 2) How these changed user behaviors, emerging mental models transform traditional web based information retrieval service and what are the futuristic models that reflect those trends and help users access information more easily?*
- 3) If the agent-based web information retrieval service could be the one of futuristic model that is able to represents recent changes in user behaviors, mental model and limitations such as a mobility, personalized media and small sized yet high resolution physical screen, then how it will look like? What is the best approach to relate the graphic user design of our service Inform Me with those factors intimately?*

Our approach is close to the general design process: **Background research- Concept development - Detail design - Implementation and Prototyping to test-** iteration. This process was beginning with research on people's context -user, business, technology - which derived to find users needs given emerging technology and innovative service model.

ON-THE-SPOT APPLICATION OF RESEARCH

In the last stage of this research improving search results accuracy, a tragic tsunami suddenly hit the east side of Japan. Following Japan's catastrophic earthquake and tsunami, severed undersea lines, downed antennas and overall infrastructure damage compromised both land lines and wireless communications. For this reason, people could not use any kinds of telecommunication network except wireless internet service for almost one week. Since our research prototype is developed on Google's AppspotService(<http://j-shuttle.appspot.com>), we decided to release this service for users wishing that it would be any help to find valuable internet resources for people who are suffered from this tragic situation though it still had small technical issues. Fortunately, during this period, our application prototype Inform Me was widely used among Korean students who are studying in Japan and several Japanese students in order to collect break news, to contact their families, friends within internet communities and to find resources for first aid methods. Thus, we found that generally this application was able to successfully adopted and helped people to find internet resources in several cases.

Figure 1. A tragic occasion happened in Japan

BACKGROUND RESEARCH

The social and cultural trend research was conducted dealing with users needs. The results extended to grab insights and main stream especially in urban life. From literature review, the authors developed the figure 2 presenting human's life mega streams. To drill down users needs dealing with belonging and self esteem/ expression, additional user research methodology including FGI and Informal Interview was conducted under habitual process. The samples for user research were all paid participants who spend times for smart phones and mobile internet services. In figure 1, the first column shows hot issues to the society. People have handheld information appliances including smart phones, PDA or network book collecting the information and seeking them in a short time. Second column explains human innate nature obtained from desk research. It shows people are familiar with not only official internet media articles but also prefer to gather information from various private sources. And they also wanted to both consume and share their interests for ensuring their interests, curiosity repeatedly using their niche time.

Figure 2. Recent user trends of Internet Use

Figure 3. Results and Findings from User Studies

Once desk research was done, we conducted informal face to face interview and focus group discussion with paid participants under habitual process. 20 people were participated and their average age is 26 ranging from 23 - 28. 15 males and 5 females are participated. Two moderators went through FGI with open and ended questionnaire to find their needs dealing with information in the various situations in everyday.

Figure 4. Shots from In-Depth User Interviews

The results show several insights and problematic keywords for designing an agent-based web information retrieval service within urban users:

Niche time usage behavior The more information and mobile communication technology is developed, the more people intend to use their time with efficiency and density than before. It means that people have a desire to use their every single minute doing multiple tasks even they are moving or resting instead of remaining their time as a dead time, monotonous time or stand-still time. According to Lee, this special user behavior or social trend could be described as a 'Niche Time Usage.'

Less is more The vast range of unknown and unnecessary information overwhelms and frustrates users, making the original targeted information overly complex. Desired or information or resources needed are often not even discovered.

Familiarity Users prefer still familiar information retrieval, acquisition process and methodology. Exploring or learning new behaviors is an unwanted burden to the users.

Lack of clarity Core features reside together with fringe benefits. Users easily get lost with cryptic icons and complex navigation models.

I'm not stupid Users want their need for simplicity to be treated with respect for only they are interested in. Over-friendly information and recommendations are not welcomed, they just only to insult them.

Size matters Handheld information appliances and phones are becoming too small with button labels, icons and texts getting harder to read, and buttons becoming too fiddly and close to each other.

Time is precious Users do want to spend minimized time on acquiring and managing information that they wanted to seek and consume.

PROBLEMS OF WEB-BASED INFORMATION RETRIEVAL

The characteristics of the information content of the web and its dynamics determine a different kind of problem with different tasks to be carried out and the approaches to perform those tasks. In here, we briefly address these issues in order to describe the traditional web-based search process.

Large size the information base on the Web is huge with billions of web pages.

Unlabeled the content and the keywords summarizing the content are not sufficient to categorize the information base.

Duplicated there may be more than one copies of the same information distributed on the web.

Semi-structured currently there are no set structures describing the format of each and every content. HTML tags are the ones used most frequently.

FUTURE CHALLENGES TO SMART-AGENT BASED INFORMATION RETRIEVAL IN URBAN AREAS

Comprehensive coverage due to the large size of the information base, the system should be able to retrieve information from all possible locations of the resources within the complicated structure and large size of the web.

Effective discovery The agent should be fast and effective in responding to relevance and ranking requirements and bring useful search results.

Contextual The system should be able to handle incomplete, imprecise data and often rely on contextual information.

Adaptive It has to be adaptive in many respects including query modifications, interface and usability.

Effective content delivery: The system should be able to rank, summarize, personalize the content for precision in delivery.

Easy to use: it should be easy and flexible to use in various unstable situation such as in buses, MRTs or in the middle of large shopping malls.

CONCEPT DEVELOPMENT

Two approaches, in general, may apply to develop concept of project or service. One is bottom up approach. It is important to be generating as many ideas as possible and clustering into meaningful chunks with keywords, so it can be thought about. Making, then, a conceptual model of the data, but even looking at the data laid out in any sort of way should be enough for the designer to begin to draw design implication from it. The other is top down. It is to be setup an idea about what the product or service is going to be needed to appear once the research is done. It encourages to be beginning to suggest solutions to pursue. In the present study, authors chose the second methods when developing service concept. Because, it is more efficient way for designer to start digging in and actually designing something. In order to solve various frustrated experiences that authors got inspired from user studies, we were drawing of a concept of smart agent.

Figure 5. Basic Working Framework for InformMe Agent

Our fundamental concept, a smart agent is able to be defined that a software based robot which is seeking various resources on the web or conducting diverse tasks without users' intervention or management when they are running for gathering

information. Almost of all smart agents use a standards protocol which is called KQML(Knowledge Query and Manipulation Language) in order to retrieve proper information that is able to fit users' needs and desire communicating various web servers, agents.

DETAILED DESIGN GUIDELINE FOR INTERFACE

From user studies, authors could analysis and find insights to design a graphical user interface that is to achieve the users' goal and perception towards our agent based web information retrieval service

In terms of Familiarity:

Iconic expression of button layout

- Common nominator of key layout across industry
- Minimal, but not simplistic
- Iconic through simplicity
- Make the service behave like other familiar apps
- Apply PC interface metaphors like pulldown menus, floating windows etc.
- Lowers learning curve

In terms of Clarity:

Avoid competing redundancy and maintain grid

- Avoid the branding or Ad playground
- Only use one consistent navigation system
- Contextual search results compete with contents
- Initial impression is complexity

Clear visual language and iconography

- Apply icons sparsely
- Icons should be legible, avoid overly rich or confusing styling
- Apply colors to support icon language

Scalability

Make the interface scale well for content lists, if 5 or 500 entries

- Short-cuts can arise out of existing behavior (e.g. increase speed with constant button press)

In terms of Straightforwardness:

Prioritization

- Prioritize core functionality: lists and categories
- 20% of the functions are being used 80% of the time
- Bring core functionality to the surface
- Merge alike formats into one location and organize by context

Figure 6. Major Screenshots from Prototype

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Our prototype is meant to be designed to predict the futuristic mobile information retrieval service and its user behavior. Thus, in order to get a practical, insightful results and findings, a final user evaluation was conducted in the actual situations rather to under strictly controlled circumstances.

We recruited 20 users who are well aware of mobile phones and have appropriate digital media literacy also to use internet resources well. Same as our initial stage, 20 people in total were participated and their average age is 26 ranging from 23 - 28. Fifteen male and five female are participated, however, they are not same individuals.

Each participant was tested individually. All participants were first asked to come to the Seoul National University to complete a general information questionnaire concerning his/her demographic information, experience with the internet and with mobile services, attitude towards information retrieval in general and involvement. An introduction of the purpose and tasks of the experiment was then given. The participant was

asked to get back to their home, office or university completing three tasks at each place, as listed on a task sheet.

Items	1pt	2	3	4	5	6	7pt	(point)
Overall								Overall
Disliking	4%	4%	9%	34%	30%	14%	5%	Liking
Bad	2%	2%	8%	39%	30%	14%	4%	Good
Uninteresting	4%	2%	13%	30%	31%	14%	5%	Interesting
Useless	4%	4%	8%	23%	32%	25%	5%	Useful
Irritating	8%	6%	18%	36%	20%	7%	5%	Not Irritating

Figure 7. Attitude towards agent based web information retrieval service in general

As a result, mobile users showed a modestly positive attitude towards agent based web information retrieval service in general. 48% considered such process and results "overall liking", 48% considered them "good", 50% considered them "interesting", and more encouragingly, 62% considered them "useful". Irritation is a controversial issue because we could not analysis this opinions were derived from our fundamental concept or only GUI problem at this moment, however, as reflected by the static that 32% found them "irritation", 32% "not irritation", and the rest 36% gave a neutral response. According to respondents' satisfaction ratings, they were classified into "positive respondents" (people whose satisfaction ratings were higher than 4) and "negative respondents" (people whose satisfaction ratings were lower than 4) for each type of new web information retrieval service. Significant differences were found in age between positive and negative respondents, indicating that young people are more enthusiastic for this kind of new information seeking approach which is enable to hold multiple tasks at a time and refine their initial queries.

CONCLUSION

Through human centered process, the present paper presents vision of future mobile information retrieval and concept proof scenarios. Through Inform Me service, the authors are trying to open a way to use valuable internet resources in diverse situation in daily urban life. Inform Me which is suggested by authors is an attempt to address the changing trends in user behaviors including mental models especially in mobile phone information retrieval process within

complex urban areas. Authors also make all their effort to relieve users' cognitive load by using a smart agent bot. They also find a way to improve the quality of search results by adopting a new approach by adding a context, intension search keywords before the bot actually get operated.

The more information will be generated, the users' cognitive loads will be also heavier and heavier. For that reason, we expect that this sort of smart agent based services, ontological services will be thriving. It would be needed more focus both on users' information retrieval behavior in urban areas and interaction between users and handheld information appliances.

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